

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF LINGUISTICS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Mukhiddinova Marjona

is a second-year student of

Philology and language teaching: French

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Annotatsiya: Tilshunoslik fanining o'qitilishi, uning tarixiy jarayoni haqida bayon qilish. Olimlar: Mahmud Koshg'ariy, Zamaxshariy va O'rta Osiyolik olimlarning tilshunoslik rivojiga qo'shgan hissalarini. Annotatsiya Rus olimi Lomonosovning taqdiqotlari ifodalangan. Tilshunoslik o'qitishning metod va usullari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Abstract: Description of the teaching of linguistics, its historical process. Scientists: Mahmud Koshghari, Zamakhshari and the contributions of the Central Asian scientists to the development of linguistics. The researches of the Russian scientist Lomonosov are expressed. Methods and methods teaching linguistics are discussed.

Аннотация: Описание преподавания языкознания, его исторического процесса. Ученые: Махмуд Кошгари, Замахшари и вклад ученых Центральной Азии в развитие языкознания. Выражены исследования русского ученого Ломоносова. Обсуждаются метод и метод преподавания языкознания.

Key words: linguistics, language, method, automatic, experimental phonetic, ЕНМ, acoustic method

We all know that linguistics, that is, linguistics, is the science of this language, its social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of operation of certain languages, and historical development. Well, we have such a question. Why do we need linguistics? Why do we study it as a science? Let's answer these two questions first. There is a person for whom language plays an important role in his life. A country without a language, that is, without its own language, cannot rise or develop. Now let's talk about teaching it as a science. It should be noted that in all higher education institutions specializing in language teaching, students are taught linguistics. Because of this, it is impossible to imagine a nation without a language. According to its purpose and task, linguistics is divided into several directions: general linguistics, special linguistics, applied linguistics, etc. Linguistics has many branches and branches that study specific levels and units in each language. Of these, semasology studies the meanings of language units, phonetics and phonology examine the sound construction of the language. Linguistics as a science allowed to study native and foreign languages,

develop and improve terminology, scientific interpretation of linguistic texts and draw theoretical conclusions for their correct understanding.

The study of linguistic problems begins with Ancient India. Ancient Indian linguistics emerged as a result of linguistic interpretation of the Vedas, which were created before the 6th century BC. Central Asian scientists such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Koshgari and Zamakhshari made a great contribution to the development of Turkic linguistics. While Ibn Sina investigated sounds from the phoneme point of view, Javhari, Koshghari and Zamakhshari made great innovations in world linguistics in the field of lexis and lexicography. In addition, Mahmud Koshghari and Zamakhshariy with their "Devonu Lugotit-Turk" and "Muqaddimat ul-Adab" works, by comparing and contrasting Turkish dialects and languages belonging to different families, made a comparative-historical contribution to linguistics. who made a name for themselves as the first linguists who used method and typology. M.V. Lomonosov's work "IRus phammatica" consistently describes the phonetic, morphological, and partially syntactic features of the Russian literary language for the first time. The study of the Uzbek language in the current sense began in the 20s of the 20th century. Well, now let's think about the methods of language learning, let's explain how it affects. For example, the methods of analyzing the native language and the methods of analyzing foreign languages, the methods of studying the sociological aspects of the language and the methods of analyzing speech sounds are very different from each other. There are certain guidelines for the application of research methods related to each discipline, which constitute the working methodology of this discipline. So, if the method is a way of knowing, the methodology is a guide used in the way of knowing. There is also a general methodology of each science, which is a teaching about research methods of science. For example, we are now descriptive Let's explain the method. This method is considered to be the most ancient and the first leading method of world linguistics, works related to ancient Arabic, Greek, Indian, Chinese, Roman languages and grammars were created based on this method. The descriptive method is a method of synchronous analysis, which studies the object based on the data provided in its standing position. The information obtained by the descriptive method is the basis for all methods. Several analytical methods are used to express this.

Social - sociological method - studies the thematic grouping of words, their position, normative-methodical features.

2 Pronunciation-auditory features of speech sounds, analysis of phonetic phenomena are studied by the pronunciation-acoustic method. In this, the method of experimental phonetic analysis is especially important. In this method, phonetic phenomena such as speech sounds, intonation, pause, rhythm are studied with the help of special technical means and tools. In addition, there is also a method of electronicization of linguistic units. This is also called automatic analysis method. This method is one of the modern analysis methods created by the demand of the times, and its uniqueness is that by using computers, electronic computing machines (EHM) transfer the content of linguistic units from one language to another language by dividing the language into certain parts, linguistic units, and formal parts. is translated automatically by a computer. To do this, first a system of rules is created, which enables the translation of the text, and then a program is created to write these rules in machine language, that is, to implement these rules. Programs and dictionaries are filled with special conditional symbols.

Here, we got a little acquainted with the methods of linguistics. Now we have one more thing to think about. To what extent are we teaching this science, to what extent are we delivering it to young people? We don't know which way the young people are going. They use foreign words in every sentence, isn't this a betrayal of the language? Many of us are running away from our own national cultures and adopting aspects of foreign cultures that are not typical of our own. We will definitely have to take the positive side of learning a foreign language and their culture. Do not forget that losing nationality means losing tomorrow. What a beautiful language we have. We should mention it with pride, be happy that we are children of this country and this nation. After all, this language, this sky, and this land belong to all of us. Only when we all come together can we become a big team and do great things.

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